

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) of the Sulphides of Selenium (IV), Tellurium (IV) and Vanadium (V) obtained with Potassium Thiocarbonate (PTC)*

N. K. Kaushik and K. N. Johri

Unlike the conventional use of H_2S as precipitant, potassium thiocarbonate (PTC) yields sulphides of selenium (IV), tellurium (IV) and vanadium (V) conforming to the stoichiometric composition of SeS_2 , TeS_2 and V_2S_5 , respectively. The procedure of precipitation in each case is based on the acidification of the thiocarbonato-complex, initially obtained with excess PTC. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) not only confirms the purity of the precipitated products but determines correct temperature ranges for the precipitates to attain constant weight affording gravimetric estimation of Se, Te and V.

Analytical applications of Potassium thiocarbonate (PTC) reagent, replacing the conventional use of gaseous hydrogen sulphide in qualitative¹⁻³ and quantitative^{4,5} analysis of metal ions, have been extensively studied. Aqueous form of standard^{6,7} PTC being easy to prepare and store, is usually used after suitable dilution of the stock solution. In the present communication, studies on thermogravimetric analysis⁸ of the samples of Selenium (IV), Tellurium (IV) and Vanadium (V) sulphides obtained with PTC have been reported.

Thermogravimetric analysis permits the sample to be simultaneously weighed while it is actually being heated in the furnace and thus provides a continuous record of weight change against heating-time. Since the temperature of the furnace is increased at a steady rate, a graph of weight against temperature is obtained. The widest application of thermogravimetric analysis lies in investigating analytical procedures for determining suitable and stable weighing forms of elements or their compounds within specified limits of temperature. The main aim is to obtain information relating to the decomposition and drying characteristics of gravimetric precipitates, essential requirement being a horizontal portion of the curve in a plot of weight against temperature. Such a study of metal sulphides obtained with Potassium thiocarbonate (PTC) reagent has not been carried out as gathered from literature⁸. Thermogravimetric data in this respect would also determine: (a) Any deviation from their stoichiometric compositions, establishing the extent of purity

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of the metal sulphides precipitated with PTC. (b) Nature of precipitates gained at various experimental circumstances, (c) Difference in the thermolysis of metal sulphides resulting from the use of PTC as against the products obtained with other thio-reagents (hydrogen sulphide, sodium sulphide, thioacetamide or thiosulphate etc.). (d) Correct temperature ranges for the gravimetric estimation of constituent metal ions as sulphide or oxides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and Chemicals: An aqueous solution of PTC (1M) prepared by modified direct method was used as stock solution and its working solutions obtained by suitable dilutions were used as precipitant.

Metal Ion Solutions: Aqueous solutions of Sodium selenite, Potassium tellurite and Ammonium Vanadate were prepared using their analytical grade (B.D.H; AnalaR or Merck, G.R.) samples.

Preparation of the Sulphides: As noticed in literature there is some degree of uncertainty with regard to the mode of preparation, nature and stability of sulphides of Selenium, Tellurium and Vanadium when hydrogen sulphide is used as precipitant. This is especially so in the case of TeS_2 and V_2S_5 . However, potassium thiocarbonate (PTC) when used in excess to form the respective thiocarbonate complexes prior to their acidification with HCl, yield definite products in all the three cases. Aqueous solns. containing 30 mg of the metal ions per 100 ml were treated with an aq. 0.5M soln. of PTC added dropwise and stirring constantly till a soluble coloured thiocarbonato-complex was obtained. Subsequent acidification of the colored product with 1.5-2N hydrochloric acid followed by digestion on steam bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour resulted in the precipitation of the sulphide in each case.

After cooling the precipitate, it was collected by filtration through Whatman filter paper No. 42. After thorough washing with water and finally with alcohol the product was dried at room temperature under suction for over 4 hr.

Thermorecording Balance used: The thermogravimetric data was collected using a Stanton's Thermorecording Balance model TR-I, installed at the Central Road Research Institute, New Delhi.

Thermogravimetric Procedure: A weighted sample of dried metal sulphide (250 mg) was transferred to a crucible freshly tarred to 1000° and subsequently stored in a desiccator. The sample was subjected to a heating rate of $4 \pm 0.2^\circ$ per minute in an atmosphere of air. The data were collected for a range of temperature up to 1000° . The period of maximum rise in temperature was about 4 hr. The sensitivity of the balance per small chart division was 1 mg and chart range 100 mg. All data used in the preparation of the thermogravimetric curves were corrected for buoyancy (experimentally determined for the crucible used). The thermograms shown were obtained by plotting different points of the original graph on X- and Y- axes. All the instructions for operating the Stanton's Thermobalance, as given in the brochure supplied with the instrument, were strictly followed.

Thermogravimetric Behaviour of Selenium Sulphide: Thermal behaviour of Selenium (IV) sulphide, as precipitated with sodium sulphide, has already been studied by Taimni

and Tandon⁹ and according to them it is stable up to 210° when it begins to sublime. The present thermolysis studies of SeS₂ (lemon-yellow product) obtained with potassium thiocarbonate (PTC) shows a similar trend in weight-change to that of the product obtained with sodium sulphide by Taimni⁹. As seen in the thermogram represented by fig. 1, the disulphide remains stable up to 200° after which it shows a loss in weight, first slow between the temperature range 200° to 312° and then rapid, finally showing complete loss to 500°. This slow loss in weight initially is found to be due to the oxidation of the disulphide to dioxide, SeO₂. The oxide starts subliming at 312° and its sublimation is complete by 500°. This temperature range for the sublimation of SeO₂ is confirmed from literature.

FIG. 1: THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF SELENIUM(IV) SULPHIDE(SeS₂).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2: THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF TELLURIUM(IV) SULPHIDE (TeS₂).

FIG. 2

Thermogravimetric Behaviour of Tellurium (IV) Sulphide: The thermogram of Tellurium (IV) sulphide (fig. 2) shows that the sulphide is stable up to 180° when it begins to decompose into elementary tellurium, the resulting loss in weight is observed up to 360°. From 360° to 420° the curve is not strictly horizontal due to the slight increase in weight (3 mg) showing the start of oxidation. However, beyond 420° the weight increases progressively up to 660°, after which it remains constant till 800°. The weight between 660°-800° corresponds to the required weight of TeO₂. As expected, TeO₂ begins subliming at 800°. According to Taimni and Tandon¹⁰ tellurium disulphide precipitated with sodium sulphide has shown almost similar trend in weight change with rise in temperature. According to Taimni there is initially a progressive loss in weight between 180° and 370° and then remains constant up to 410° corresponding to the weight of elementary tellurium. A gain in weight from 410° to 620° confirms the formation of the dioxide, TeO₂.

Thermogravimetric Behaviour of Vanadium(V) Sulphide: Although Taimni and Agarwal¹¹ have studied the precipitation of Vanadium sulphide with Arsenic group member cations by using (NH₄)₂S_x as precipitating agent, but they have not studied the thermal behaviour of the product. The present thermolysis studies of V₂S₅, as precipitated from the thiocarbonate complex initially obtained with excess FTC reagent, agrees quite closely with the stoichiometry of V₂S₅. The thermogram of V₂S₅ (dark brown product) is given in fig. 3. The initial colloidal nature of the product enables it to retain occluded (250°-300°) water and sulphur during precipitation. This water and adsorbed sulphur

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are released over a large temperature interval till the temperature has reached 240°. As Vanadium pentasulphide does not produce any horizontal level, the sulphide weighing form of Vanadium cannot yield accurate results. However, the resultant oxide V_2O_5 remains unchanged from 300° onwards and follows a horizontal course which extends as far as 1000°.

FIG. 3. THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF VANADIUM(V) SULPHIDE (V_2S_5).

FIG. 3

It is concluded that the product of SeS_2 as obtained with PTC is pure confirming to the stoichiometric composition. Furthermore, the thermolysis reveals two-stage transformation of SeS_2 , first to SeO_2 and then the sublimation of the oxide, rather than the outright sublimation of SeS_2 starting at 210°, as reported by Taimni⁹. Clean precipitation of selenium disulphide being possible with PTC as precipitant, the product after drying up to 200° can be quantitatively weighed for its estimation.

Tellurium can be separated as stable sulphide with PTC as precipitant and estimated either as disulphide after drying upto 180°, but due to the wide horizontal level between 660° and 800° estimation of tellurium as dioxide would be preferable, after its separation as sulphide with PTC.

Separation of Vanadium (V) as pentasulphide being possible with PTC, its gravimetric estimation as oxide, V_2O_5 after igniting the sulphide above 300° would be accurate. The temperature range for the constancy in weight of the oxide is 300°-1000°.

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